

IMPROVING FOOD INDUSTRY STANDARDS IN AZERBAIJAN: UNDERSTANDING GAPS AND PROPOSING EFFECTIVE SOLUTIONS

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Abstract -

This study aims to evaluate the current state of the food industry in Azerbaijan, focusing on main problems in produced product's quality and gaps in the regulations over the food market. Currently with the increasing trend of consumerism among the population, many problems have emerged regarding the food industry which are so detrimental for the population's health. This paper highlights the reasons why the government should worry about those gaps in the regulations and problems in the food industry. It investigates future risks of those gaps and provides some suggestions to eliminate these gaps and improve food quality. Through case studies and practical solutions this article emphasizes the role of regulations in driving food quality and offers insights into overcoming common challenges in implementing those regulations.

Keywords: food industry, bad-quality products, gaps in regulation, food quality improvement, population's health,

Introduction:

At the moment Azerbaijan has undergone radical changes due to globalization and the opening of the market to international trade. Food industry in the country is expanding with its fastest speed and consumers demand on the food suppliers is increasing at the same pace with the trending globalization which shifted dietary habits from traditional, nutrient-dense diets to sugar-rich and processed alternatives, causing local market to be occupied by junk and ultra-processed foods that are easily imported to the country and sold.

With unchecked development of the food industry, there have been many gaps that occurred over the time, that regulatory systems couldn't catch their pace to prevent those gaps from occurring. Nowadays even though there are many important steps that have been done to increase food quality within the country such as Azerbaijan Food Safety Institute, yet, there are still rooms that need to be improved. Public is at the beginning of that trending fast eating fashion and if appropriate precautions are not taken into consideration, the health sector may get stuck in many problems. While international recommendations exist to guide stakeholders' actions to create healthy food environments, the extent to which these recommendations align with public and private sector commitments and progress is still mainly unknown.

Rising Trends in Obesity and Diabetes: A Call for Action in Azerbaijan

Obesity has been referred to as a 'pandemic' situation (Meldrum et al. 2017). This situation has progressed gradually between 1985 and 2017, when high body mass index (BMI) emerged in both rural and urban populations. (LMICs) (NCD-RisC 2019).

High BMI is frequently associated with cardiovascular disease, ranking as the fourth leading risk factor for mortality and disease burden in 2017 (GBD 2017 Risk Factor Collaborators 2018). Branca et al. (2019) emphasized that unhealthy diets, all forms of malnutrition (including obesity) and noncommunicable diseases are interrelated problems and that the current food system must be repositioned towards high-quality diets for all. In response to such data, the United Nations (UN) called for structural changes in food environments and urgent action by the food industry to reduce the production, marketing and availability of unhealthy foods and sell healthier food options (UNGA 2014a).

Azerbaijan has a population of more than 10 million people (The State Statistical Committee of the Republic of Azerbaijan 2024), of which almost 28% was obese in 2019 (World obesity ranking 2022). Prevalence of obesity among adults has increased twice the amount since 1990.(WHO, Health data overview for the Republic of Azerbaijan 2024)Picture 2.

Picture 1. Deaths by -endocrine nutritional and metabolic diseases, State Statistical Committee

Picture 2. Prevalence of obesity in Azerbaijan, Global Nutrition Report,

In Azerbaijan, mortality level related to The Nutrition and Metabolic Diseases section which is actively involved in clinical and basic research pertaining to the disorders of human nutrition and metabolism such as obesity, other body fat disorders, diabetes, and hyperlipidemias, has rapidly doubled in recent years. Picture 1.

Another most remarkable change that occurred among the population is the difference between insulin dependent and independent diabetes. This significantly shows how the difference between these two types of diabetes is growing. If we look up them, Insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (IDDM), also known as type

1 diabetes, usually starts before 15 years of age. When a person develops type 1 diabetes, the pancreas stops making insulin. To help the body’s cells use the glucose, a child with type 1 diabetes mellitus (DM) must receive insulin by injection.

The other type of diabetes is type 2, non-insulin dependent diabetes mellitus (NIDDM). Type 2 diabetes is more common than type 1. About 9 out of 10 people with diabetes have type 2(The IDF Diabetes Atlas). Type 2 DM used to occur mostly in adults, but is becoming increasingly more common in children and it is associated with obesity.

Picture 3.

Morbidity of the population with diabetes type 1 and type 2, State Statistical Committee of Azerbaijan(SSCA).

So, after the information mentioned above, we can see how type 2 diabetes, which is gained most of the time by having bad quality food and less physical activity, surged up in Picture 3. Therefore, it is important to say what made type 2 diabetes increase whereas type 1 diabetes decreased. Probably, improvement in the healthcare system helped many to save from type 1 diabetes but on the other hand, too many unhealthy foods in the market and lifestyle of people, made many have type 2 diabetes unfortunately. From picture 2, it is obvious that detrimental effects of plentiness of unhealthy food in the diet of people are causing growth in the numbers of emerged cases of diabetes in the population, which can not be denied and it should be a motive for the government to take measures to calm down those trends in the food industry.

Challenges in Food Labeling and Ingredient Transparency in Azerbaijan

With the trending globalization, the food market in Azerbaijan is filled with poor quality food products,

while the industry lacks sufficient certifications to clarify the quality of products by which consumers would be able to easily differentiate products’ quality. Therefore, there are many gaps in the industry that need to be covered such as one huge issue in the ingredient’s list of products made in Azerbaijan.

The WHO Dietary Guidelines for Azerbaijan recommend limiting calories from added sugars to less than 10 percent of total calories per day. The recommended sugar intake will fall below 10% of total daily calories, compared to a target of 5%, the WHO said. The proposed limits apply to all sugars added to food, as well as sugars naturally found in honey, syrups, fruit juices and fruit concentrates. For example, if a person consumes a 2,000-calorie diet daily, that would be 200 calories or 50 grams of added sugar per day. Consuming too much added sugar can make it difficult to meet nutritional needs while staying within calorie limits. Added sugars listed on the Nutrition label can help people make informed choices based on individual needs and preferences. But now, products made in Azerbaijan

are lacking an important part of this process, showing the sugar amount in the ingredient list. Unfortunately, there is not any requirement in the food regulation policy of Azerbaijan that requires companies to show the sugar amount in the product they produced. As people lack this information, it is hard to talk about making informed choices as people can't follow their sugar intake daily. But sugar amount is so essential for many reasons, one reason is that it will help people to be well-informed about their decision because if they see the sugar amount, this would also support individuals who want to live healthy and abstain themselves added sugar, second reason is that if health objective is to achieve sugar intake less than 10%, then the best way to achieve it, is to show people how much sugar they consume with each product. So, absence of such an important part hinders people from making informed choices and reducing sugar consumption.

There are not that many regulations on max and min amounts of the ingredients, therefore some companies are really good players on this gap, they produce some juices but adding just syrup of a fruit which contains a little percentage of real fruit, while adding as much as sugar they want. But it is well known that there are some proportions that need to be considered such as the proportion of the fruit to all other ingredients. Also there should be some regulations on the max amount of sugar too, because sugary foods and drinks can have large amounts of calories with less nutrients, and so having too much of them can lead to weight gain and obesity. Being overweight or obese can increase the risk of diseases such as heart disease and type 2 diabetes. But as the regulatory laws in the food industry are absent of sugar limitations, companies are so willing to use as much as sugar they want, so that they can make their products as compatible as possible without considering health issues they caused.

Azerbaijan's regulations for fruit content and vitamins in food products are based on international guidelines which is The Codex Alimentarius. The Codex Alimentarius is a collection of internationally recognized standards, guidelines, and codes of practice related to food safety and quality. But the issue with Codex Alimentarius is that regulations in Codex Alimentarius are not tailored to each country and they are not mandatory too, they only provide guidelines but they are implemented totally depending on the countries themselves. Therefore, Azerbaijan should aim to generate its own system for the food industry as many countries do and implement some regulations which are targeting to tackle some concerns that are also huge issues in the country of Azerbaijan. At this point, other strategies can also be considered such as warning labels and taxation strategies to reduce the amount of added sugar and

sugar consumption, particularly in drinks and snacks targeted at children, setting the minimum amount of nutrients for fruit or vitamins in packaged foods.

Leveraging Regulatory Voids: A Marketing Opportunity for Food Corporations

Overall, as there are many gaps in the food industry, companies are wisely using them for their marketing strategies to get a higher share and compete against their rivals in the market while damaging the population's health so much.

As there is no rule for showing the sugar amount on the list label of the products, companies use this gap so much because they know that customers who are aware of the effects of sugar, will not be willing to buy their products. By which they also hide even whether they did add a recommended amount of sugar per 100ml/gr. So, leaving customers with uncertainty about the sugar amount in their products, companies don't support customers to make informative decisions. This also disrupts perfect marketing too as those companies that don't display the sugar level gain an advantage over their competitors that are producing their products according to international laws and supporting customers to make healthy decisions.

Secondly, companies that produce sugary food, and beverages use the gap of not having any limitations on the sugar amount, in their marketing strategies. After the Gulf Cooperation Council (GCC) countries implemented a 50% excise tax on sugary drinks, companies shifted focus to countries like Azerbaijan, where such taxes do not exist. As of 2022, sales of sugary drinks in Azerbaijan grew by 12% annually, a rate higher than in neighboring countries with sugar taxes. Picture 5, illustrates that the production and consumption of sweetened beverages doubled since 2007. This situation shows how beverage companies impressively shifted their attention to Azerbaijan where the market is so convenient for selling, marketing their products, making huge profits, and many domestic and foreign companies in the country increased their production enormously, doubling its production size from around 20 thousands to 48 thousands between 2007 and 2023. This is a huge customer-influencing opportunity for them. It is well known that there are three main ingredients that make people love the food product, those elements are sugar, salt and fat. So, the balance of those ingredients can make a product super attractive and addictive too. And if we take the case of no regulation on the amount of sugar, then companies can consider adding such amounts of sugar in their products to keep them tasty, make clients enjoy them as much as possible, and make them addictive, without even considering health issues that sugar causes.

Picture 5. Sweetened mineral and aerated waters , thousand decalitre, SSCA

Another issue is that to implement their tricky labeling strategies, companies can benefit from the lack of appropriate labeling policy for food products. They design their products in a way which will cause misleading among customers. This is a huge issue, especially among children, as design of, characters or some other objects on the products are adjusted to influence, attract consumers and differ their products from others, and because of that, people especially children and consumers with low awareness of health are easily being trapped to choose a product by its cover even it is not recommended for morning meal or to eat that product in high amounts. Also, ingredient lists, and other informative labels on the products are placed in a way that isn't easily visible, so companies can influence customers just by showing what they want to show to them.

Companies are highly adept on adding the addictive sugar amount, using some provoking objects or characters, hiding informative labels, and implementing attractive design strategies on their products with the help of marketing, that knows the gaps in the regulations and can easily promote their products but if proper regulations exist such as warning labels, limiting

and taxing over sugar and etc in the food industry, it wouldn't be possible for companies to hide the truth and affect the consumers' health that much. If there would be taxing over sugar, companies wouldn't be eager to add as much as sugar they want, as they also need to consider costs of adding extra sugar, if there would be warning labels about high amount of sugar, fat, salt, it wouldn't be possible for companies to escape truth, being informative, and to hide how unhealthy they are.

Traditional Cuisine and Its Role in Modern Health Challenges.

As can be seen from the daily diet of the population of Azerbaijan, a huge part of people like to eat and try new flavors but also on the other hand are more prone to consume fat, sugary, salty food (high-calorie, carbohydrate-rich, oily foods). Picture 6 and 7 depicts that situation clearly, showing which elements in the population's nutritional intake are trending from 2000 to 2023. There is an increasing trend in consumption of industrial processed food products such as margarine, salt, sugary products, while juices, vegetable oils, and cheeses still remain the same. These trends say a lot about the daily diet of the population and where the gaps are.

Picture 6 and 7, SSCA

Consumption of main industrial processed food products per capita, annual, kilogram

Picture 7. Consumption of main industrial processed food products per capita, annual, kilogram

Meals in local cuisine are mostly composed of such elements and most of the time domestic people like to eat a huge portion of sugary foods, dramatically in a decade the population's consumption of cake, confectionery and other baked goods raised from around 43 thousands to 73 thousands ton between 2007 and 2023(SSCA). Almost the entire population has adapted to this eating pattern, it is in the traditions of the society, thereby the population can be influenced by their eating habits more than anything else. So, while nutrition is a huge part of the population's lifestyle, it is also the weakest and most problematic part of their lives as it opens many doors for companies to influence them. If society and responsible institutions don't

take this job seriously, it can cause huge issues among the population such as obesity, diabetes, and other metabolism related health issues which are trending nowadays dramatically.

Tackling the Gaps: Practical Solutions to Improve Food Standards

So far, only gaps and the issues they caused have been discussed.

Now let's see how problematic gaps in the food industry in Azerbaijan can be handled to reduce the rising prevalence of diet-related diseases and increase food quality. To this end, some strategies that are most appropriate to the circumstances of the population will be discussed with examples of other countries that have successfully implemented in their food industry.

Starting with the sugar amount, taxing over sugar level per product is one of the best strategies that can impact sugar amount effectively and already many have successfully implemented this strategy to force companies to reformulate their products.

One successful taxing regulation was implemented in the UK.

The UK introduced a sugar tax (SDIL) in 2018, which applies to drinks with more than 5 grams of sugar per 100ml. There are two bands: Low Band drinks with 5-8 grams of sugar per 100ml are taxed at a lower rate. High Band drinks with more than 8 grams of sugar per 100ml are taxed at a higher rate. This tax has encouraged manufacturers to reduce sugar levels in soft drinks to avoid the levy. As a result, now if we take an example of a bottle of Fanta purchased in a store in Britain, some of the sugar has been replaced with a sweetener, reducing the sugar content to 4.5gr per 100ml but a typical US Fanta has 13.5g of sugar per 100ml, which is a huge improvement in the term of health. After implementation of taxes, Coca-Cola UK launched Coke zero sugar, a reformulated version of Coca-Cola Classic, which gained a 50% market share within 3 years, and sugar content in soft drinks decreased by 28% between 2015 and 2020 and tax revenues funded public health.

Modeling studies predict that SSB taxes can lead to significant reductions in disability-adjusted life years, prevalence and incident rates of obesity and type 2 diabetes, and dental caries, as well as health care expenditures, provided a sufficiently large tax rate is applied (Bourke and Veerman 2018, Saxena et al. 2019), which shows how impactful taxes actually can be for society as well as the environment.

Coming to the design of products, the bad effects of them can easily be observed, especially among the children as companies most of the time target kids since they are the ones most vulnerable to falling into the trap of marketing strategies.

The Mexican food agency implemented a nice policy, restricting putting animal mascots on children's products. The manufacturers have to remove the triggers, elephants and other animal characters from cereal boxes. These images are ingrained in the memory of so many children and all are part of a marketing strategy to boost sales and brand loyalty. It is a great tool to force companies to rearrange their labels for a new version and different packaging which are helping people make their decisions. Mexico also imposes mandatory front-of-pack labeling for foods and beverages that exceed certain sugar limits. Products containing more than 10 grams of sugar per 100 grams (solid foods) or 5 grams per 100 ml (liquid products) must display a warning label stating that they are "high in sugar." With those strategies, sales of sugary drinks declined by 12% within the first year, while water and low-sugar alternatives saw a 4% increase in sales and Nestlé reformulated products aimed at children to include more natural sugars from fruits, reducing added sugar levels by 25% in flagship items like yogurts.

There are many countries such as France, Belgium, Germany, Luxembourg, the Netherlands, Spain and Switzerland, that are implementing Nutri-Score labeling. It has a range from A to E, the green 'A' stands for healthy and the red 'E' for less healthy and it is using a nutrient profiling system that considers energy, saturated fat, sugar, and salt as negative factors and fiber, protein, and percentages of fruits, vegetables, nuts, and legumes as positive factors. The biggest benefit of this regulation is that it mitigates the process of decision making for customers and saves them from giving too much effort to make sure if a product is good enough to buy and even being trapped into marketing strategies of the companies, overall which can increase the number of healthy decisions significantly and lower overweights among the countries.

Another super merit of that case is that companies immediately start working on increasing the quality of their products even before these regulations are implemented as they also knew that if those indicators reveal how bad their product is, this means a huge loss of reputation among its customers. In order to keep their customers as well as to be able to compete against others, companies eagerly improve their products' quality. For example, Nestlé reformulated cereals to reduce sugar by 30% and Danone, improved yogurt recipes to move from D to B.

With these labeling strategies, governments can reduce overweight levels significantly.

Researchers at the NIH investigated whether people ate more calories when exposed to a diet composed of ultra-processed foods compared with a diet composed of unprocessed foods. Despite the ultra-processed and unprocessed diets being matched for daily presented calories, sugar, fat, fiber, and macronutrients, people consumed more calories when exposed to the ultra-processed diet as compared to the unprocessed

diet. Furthermore, people gained weight on the ultra-processed diet and lost weight on the unprocessed diet. Limiting consumption of ultra-processed food may be an effective strategy for obesity prevention and treatment. (Kevin D. Hall et al.). So as companies apply those labeling strategies and more healthy ingredients into their products to sustain in the market, thereby the amount of healthy ingredients in products and healthy food choices will increase by the help of labels and which means people will intake less calories, help themselves from being overweight and getting metabolic diseases.

So, designing products properly, and having some regulations on their labels, can really be impactful for the food industry as well as population's health, as many companies are trapping population and selling their products easily by hiding harmful information inside a chaotic ingredient list, not making them visible. But, with the right labeling and designing strategies, governments can help people make healthier decisions and overcome these challenges, encouraging companies to add informative labels and to increase healthy content in products.

Setting policies to put the right proportions of ingredients in a product is another best strategy that society would substantially benefit from. According to the Ordinance on fruit juice (LEX-FAOC089235), there are some proportions of ingredients a fruit juice drink must contain such as fruit juice and drinks for citrus juices should contain at least 6%, pome fruit and grape juices at least 30% and other fruit juices must contain at least 10% fruit. But in the real scenario of Azerbaijan, it is not like that, what can be seen on the ingredient lists, most of the time are just 0.1% added fruit dust or just syrup of that fruit which is full of sugar again. Therefore, there should be some regulations on the max and min amount of main ingredients of products to discourage companies from doing so. For example, in EU regulations, Fortified foods and foods making health claims must meet specific minimum ingredient thresholds under Regulation (EC) No 1925/2006 and Regulation (EU) No 1169/2011. Any food product fortified with vitamins or minerals, the added amount must contribute a significant quantity, defined as 15% of the Recommended Daily Allowance (RDA) per 100 g (solids) or per 100 mL (liquids). Infant Formula and Baby Foods (Regulation (EU) No 609/2013), must contain specific minimum amounts of nutrients, such as Vitamin D: 1 µg/100 kcal, Iron: 0.3 mg/100 kcal.

Another good strategy is to restrict advertising unhealthy foods. It is well known that what makes unhealthy products so attractive and popular is not only their ingredients, but also their advertising strategies. These advertisements encourage people to buy more of their products and distract them from making healthy choices by constantly reminding them of their products. Therefore, taking away this opportunity from companies producing unhealthy products could be truly dramatic for them, but also very beneficial for society, especially for children, since children are the main target group of these companies.

In Chile, foods and drinks that receive the "High in Sugar" label are prohibited from being advertised to

children. This includes sugary drinks, sweets and snacks, which effectively regulates sugar content by incentivizing manufacturers to comply with these restrictions. As a result, major breakfast cereal brands reduced sugar from 12g/100g to 4.9g/100g and many soft drink manufacturers reformulated their beverages to have 2.4g/100ml instead of the previous 6-8g. The biggest impact of those regulations is seen in Kellogg's Cereals. Kellogg's reduced sugar levels in popular cereals like Frosted Flakes to avoid the "High in Sugar" label and reformulated versions contained as little as 4.9g of sugar per 100g, compared to the previous 12g. Consumer sales have shifted towards these "healthier" products, reflecting higher acceptance of labeled goods. Restricting marketing unhealthy foods is a powerful tool to compel companies to switch their production for healthier offerings.

However, to tackle health issues down, not only unhealthy options needed to be worked on, but also some support need to be provided for companies producing healthy products, for instance easily being advertised everywhere, certifications with lower prices etc. which would be the incentive for companies that produce unhealthy products shift their business to healthy options to benefit from those aids.

Consequences of Inaction: The Cost of Unregulated Food Industries

Considering the current situation of some countries that do not implement policies for the benefit of society, the tragic consequences can easily be seen, how people's health level got worse and obesity level got impressively high in recent years. But not only the health sectors of countries suffer, also the environment does from that trend too, as excessive usage of unhealthy food causes environmental pollution, including air pollution that was hugely contributed by production of those ultra-processed products, and massive littering because of food waste.

The studies, published in special issues of The Lancet and Lancet Global Health on obesity, detailed worsening food-consumption habits around the world. The countries with the worst diets included Kazakhstan, Mongolia and Argentina. If Kazakhstan, one of Azerbaijan's maritime neighbors, is taken as an example, it can evidently be seen that Kazakhstan's food industry is largely unregulated concerning sugar, fat, and salt content. There are no mandatory rules for maximum sugar limits, front-of-pack nutrition labeling as well as advertisements of unhealthy foods and to make matters worse, the lack of strong labeling laws leaves consumers with limited information about the nutritional content of processed foods, which is so similar to the scenario of Azerbaijan. Looking at the country's public health, there is increasing popularity of processed foods, particularly in urban areas, leading to an increase in obesity and overweight rates, with the prevalence of obesity among adults rising to approximately 23%. The country's increasing consumption of sugar-sweetened beverages and snacks has also led to an increase in the prevalence of type 2 diabetes and hypertension.

Another nearby country is Mongolia. Mongolia has minimal regulatory frameworks regulating sugar

content, additives, or front-of-pack labeling, and advertising of sugary products and unhealthy foods is widespread and poorly monitored. As a consequence, urbanization and increasing reliance on imported processed foods have shifted dietary habits from traditional, nutrient-dense diets to sugar-rich and processed alternatives, and noncommunicable diseases such as diabetes, hypertension, and obesity are on the rise, especially in urban areas. Countries without comprehensive food industry regulations experience significant health and economic challenges and lessons from nations that introduced policies emphasize the urgent need for regulatory measures to curb the rise of diet-related diseases. The lack of comprehensive food regulations in Kazakhstan, and Mongolia highlights the challenges of addressing public health crises without government intervention.

If the sugar amount, or design of products are not properly regulated then diabetes, illnesses related to eating habits are inevitable, as even a regular person will get higher calories with no nutrients in a normal proportion of food because of high sugar content in the product, children will keep buying some well-designed food products, due to the reason that they seem so attractive. Because those kinds of products are triggering the body for overconsumption and not containing healthy portions of the ingredients enough, society will face many health risks caused by poor nutrition as it is associated with numerous diseases and health conditions.

Obesity is just one of them, which is caused by excessive consumption of processed foods, unhealthy fats, and sugary drinks. Diets high in refined carbohydrates and sugary foods increase insulin resistance and the likelihood of developing type 2 Diabetes.

To talk statistically, while just 2% of children and adolescents aged 5–19 were obese in 1990 (31 million young people), by 2022, 8% of children and adolescents were living with obesity (160 million young people) and in 2022, 2.5 billion adults were overweight, of these, 890 million were living with obesity. (WHO Obesity and overweight 1 March 2024). The IDF Diabetes Atlas (2021) reports that 10.5% of the adult population (20–79 years) has diabetes, with almost half unaware that they are living with the condition and it's no wonder around 90% of diabetes cases are type 2, heavily influenced by dietary patterns. While talking about the current issues that obesity causes in the health sector, The economic losses caused by obesity across countries cannot be ignored. The economic impact of overweight and obesity worldwide was estimated to be approximately US\$1.96 trillion in 2020. (World Obesity Federation 2022). For Azerbaijan, the economic impact of overweight and obesity was estimated to be US\$1.2 billion in 2019. This is equivalent to US\$120 per capita and 2.5% of GDP. (WOF Global obesity observation).

There are more examples proving that unhealthy diets, particularly those high in sugar, salt, and fat, are leading causes of various non-communicable diseases (NCD) all over the world.

A diet high in saturated fats, cholesterol, and sodium from processed foods can increase blood pressure

and lead to cardiovascular disease while a diet low in fruits, vegetables, and whole grains increases the risk of colorectal, breast, and prostate cancers. Insufficient intake of calcium and vitamin D can weaken bones and increase the risk of fractures. Tooth decay and gum disease are caused by unhealthy nutrition high in sugar. Inadequate nutrients impair immune function, making individuals more susceptible to infections and results in deficiencies such as anemia and vitamin deficiencies. Moreover, nutritional deficiencies, particularly omega-3 fatty acids and B vitamins, have been linked to depression and anxiety.

So, the effects of these gaps, not setting a max amount of sugar, quality requirements for most sold products, right way of labeling is traumatic and causing huge losses in both health and economic sectors among the countries.

Discussion and Conclusion

Overall, if strategies discussed above are implemented, for instance taxing over sugar level, regulating the max and min amount of some ingredients to keep products' health benefits, setting rules for labels to help people make informed decisions, Azerbaijan can experience huge progress in health and economic sectors.

Setting new regulations for labels on the food products, including sugar amount and percentage expression of Daily Value (DV) of the ingredients in the products is the best way to help people to choose healthy options and additionally to achieve The WHO Dietary Guidelines for Azerbaijan recommending limiting calories from added sugars to less than 10 percent of total calories per day. In the first place, in Azerbaijan, not having sugar amounts on the ingredient list is traumatizing this situation further but with this strategy this issue can be easily eliminated and open many options for consumers to make informed decisions and force companies to avoid hiding the sugar amount.

Implementing warning labels showing exceeded amounts of fat, salt, and sugar in the products will of course provoke many companies to reform their products to avoid those labels, as those labels are an important tool for customers to be informed about products. Therefore, companies aiming to escape loss of their customers will have to adapt their products to those new regulations to avoid those warning labels. So, that strategy can be so beneficial for society as it will increase the chances for consumers to make right decisions for their diet, and the population's daily intake will be more nutrient based, and less sugar, fat, salt content. This also can help people to reduce added sugars intake to less than 10 percent of total calories.

Quality indicators, especially ones like NutriScore labels are popular among many countries and have the biggest impact on consumers' decisions for what to buy for their next meal. Those kinds of labels showing quality of the product can help people to easily analyze products and compare them to each other so that they can smoothly switch between good and bad quality products, otherwise, it is so hard for customers to analyze if a product is good quality, and even compare them to other ones. All this process is so tiring and time consuming, but having labels indicating quality of the

product, can mitigate this huge process and reduce its burdenness, and moreover as it will facilitate the process of comparing, and decision making, consumers will also be willing to compare products to each other with their quality labels, to choose better options for themselves. Azerbaijan can adapt those many world wide known strategies for its own food market, some elements can be added specifically for the local preferences as well. Furthermore, NutriScores can encourage companies to allocate more space for healthy content. Companies will start to reform their products, reducing unhealthy content, increasing healthy substances to have a higher quality indicator on their products so that they can compete in the market against other healthier choices and be in the daily diet of the customers.

Taxing over sugar can force companies to reduce the sugar content in their products which would make their products healthier choice for the consumers, if companies do not reduce sugar amount, then products' prices will increase as a result, and it would cause a huge reduction in sales of those kind of products, which means that clients of those products now have more chances to resort to other healthier options as they broke down their habit of buying the same cheap and low-quality product by the help of price difference.

Regulating the max and min amounts of some main ingredients in food products will significantly benefit society as well as reduce the arbitrariness of companies in adding ingredients in such proportions that will lead them to save more money, and sell more of their products such as by substituting real fruit content with alternatives, adding high level of sugar in their products and etc. Therefore, this regulation can hugely increase proportions of healthy content in foods which will drastically increase the quality of those products on the scale and most importantly will help customers to have healthy options, and reduce health issues caused by malnutritions.

Limiting the maximum sugar amount is a crucial point for reducing the unhealthy food intake and obesity level among the population, as the sugar can really be so addictive and an incentive to consume more and more of a product. That's why limiting the amount of sugar in foods can help to prevent the population from consuming too much sugar, as consumers are often unaware of the amount of sugar in the products. Moreover, another big issue is that people are not well knowledgeable about whether the sugar amount shown on the products is high for them. Therefore, the government should take measures to prevent population overconsumption of sugar in the food products, by limiting the maximum amount of it, which in fact can be a good example of direct action taken towards reaching the health objectives, including reduced sugar amount, unhealthy diet, obesity level and more. People will greatly benefit from such regulation, as it will ensure they consume food with less sugar, even if they are unaware of the sugar content.

Beyond those ingredient-related regulations, one more best policy could be implemented is restricting advertisements. Unfortunately it is very well known that what makes unhealthy products also so attractive

and widely sold is not only about their content of ingredients but also their advertisement strategies. Even though people are the ones who make decisions, the market is the one that provides choices and it is obvious that customers are limited by what food companies market to them, so it is hard to talk about deliberate decisions of a person. Ads will incentivize people to buy more of their products and disrupt their attention to healthy options. That's why taking away this chance from companies producing unhealthy products can be enormously useful for society especially for children as children are the main target group of those companies since they are more vulnerable to those kinds of incentives. At this point, prohibiting the advertisement of unhealthy products especially high in sugar, can weaken companies' impact on the children, and hinder them from influencing people's decisions by their fancy advertisements. Furthermore, with that regulation, companies producing unhealthy products would go for better options and improve their products' ingredient list according to those regulations, in order to be able to advertise their products and sustain in the market which brings huge merits for society, that now what they consume would consist of better ingredients.

To sum up, there are many gaps in the food industry of Azerbaijan, for instance, not requiring sugar amount on the list of ingredients, lack of regulation on the max and min amount of harmful and beneficial content in the food products, restrictions on marketing of some unhealthy products to children, and etc. and those gaps created an convenient circumstances for companies to fill the market with junk food and are used so perfectly by companies in their marketing strategies for increasing their sales but also damaging the health of population at the same time, which is observed with a remarkable growth in the consumption of industrial processed food products such as sugar confectioneries, margarine, salt, at the same time an significant increase in the number of obesity, type 2 diabetes and other the nutrition and metabolic diseases among the population, as well as a huge rise in direct and indirect money spendings for diet-related illnesses in the healthcare system. Moreover, unfortunately this current situation is so dangerous for the population of Azerbaijan as the society is so open to any damages from the food sector because of their daily eating habits that they are more prone to eat fat, salty, sugary foods even in home cooked meals, which makes them so vulnerable in their nourishment side of life against those food companies' strategies. So, all those happenings show the urgency of that case, that if important actions are not taken before it is too late, the population can face huge difficulties in their lifestyles, it will be way harder for them to change that. Therefore, implementation of those socially beneficial regulatory strategies in the food industry, for instance warning labels, listing sugar content in ingredients, taxing excessive sugar, limiting marketing strategies of unhealthy foods, setting informative quality indicators on product designs, regulating max and min amount of necessary ingredients, can address gaps in the industry. These measures can help tackle issues such as the rise in obesity and type 2 diabetes, the mass production and importation of unhealthy products, and

the overall negative impact on public health. This, in turn, would improve society's health, enrich the food industry with healthier and more nutritional options, and reduce both direct and indirect economic losses in healthcare.

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